

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2666643>

Study of algal mediated biosynthesis of nanoparticle: future of green nanotechnology

Indranil Singh^{1*}, Sakshi Singh^{2*}

¹ Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University Madhya Pradesh, Gwalior, India

² Amity School of Engineering and Technology, Amity University Madhya Pradesh, Gwalior, India

* Correspondence: Indranil Singh, E-mail: adrasiner@gmail.com; Sakshi Singh, E-mail: ssingh@gwa.amity.edu

Received: 13 December 2018; Revised submission: 30 March 2019; Accepted: 21 April 2019

Copyright: © The Author(s) 2019. Licensee Joanna Bródka, Poland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license

(<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

ABSTRACT: Nanotechnology has today turned out to be a buzzword. Its expansion in a different field is phenomenal. But for some reason, it has been holding the rate of development. To count reason behind being its failure despite such promising properties is its high-cost production and potential harm to nature. Beside the less significant amount of production, there is a need for the eco-friendly, less toxic and cleaner method of its production. It could not have been more favorable, in case if it could lead to an increase in production at the same time in its efficiency too. Algae mediated biosynthesis of the nanoparticle is one of the probable solutions of the above-mentioned drawbacks. This review article focuses on the synthesis of nanoparticles with help of algae and their potential benefits over conventional based methods. It takes into consideration, the formation of nanoparticle through cyanobacteria, microalgae, and macroalgae.

Keywords: Algae; Biosynthesis; Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs); Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs); Nanotechnology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is the branch of science and technology that involves manipulation of material after a rigorous consolidation and significant amount of processing. Nanoparticles are formed by the number of physical, chemical or Biological procedures. Today, particles are formed through various processing technique in the vacuum or aqueous medium too [1]. It employs various processing ranging from atomic, molecular and particulate level to the chemical modification. The major drawback is the high cost of these techniques as well as the insignificant production to utilize it as a material or for the energy uses. It is the result of collaborative work of Research and development and that of the business sector. It is likely to influence various commercial sector along with the broad aspect of Medical, defense and toiletry in the upcoming future [2-3].

Drawbacks of the conventional process have led to the development of second generation nanotechnology, which is more focused about methodologies that could lead to the cleaner environment with a less harmful effect on health. It is expected and believed that microorganism like fungi, algae, and bacteria could act as a potential environment-friendly prospect of synthesis which could be clean and nontoxic [4-6]. The product in the range of 10^{-9} m with its dimension ranging from the 1 nm to 100 nm can be called as the nanomaterial or we can also call it as the nanoparticle. Basically, the nanoparticle lies in between molecular structure and those of bulk structure. In an effort by Sangeetha et al. to classify this high surface to volume

ratio particles, we could find three broad categories i.e. engineered, natural and incidental nanoparticle [7, 8].

We can also classify as the result of another work on the basis of natural and anthropogenic carbon containing nanoparticle, peptide, and DNA based nanoparticle and also the anthropogenic inorganic nanoparticle. The nanoparticle has soon become a buzzword owing to its unique properties such as optical, magnetic and thermal conductivity which has the potential to be utilized in every application. The future prospect is in diagnosis, therapeutics, electronics, wastewater treatment, remediation of the polluted environment and many more [9-11].

Green nanotechnology in particular to algae has been recently in much of researches because of its distinct benefits over other like high metal intake capability, low manufacturing cost, and friendly to the environment and cast out the burden of maintenance of culture as it is produced extracellular. Algae have a wide dimension of habitat. It can be further characterized by microalgae that are microscopic and macroalgae that are macroscopic. They could be either eukaryotic or prokaryotic with being found in the region ranging from freshwater sources to marine or hypersaline water etc. Beside the nanoparticle synthesis they too have the potential to be used as natural dyes, biofuels, enrichment of nutrition in food, and can also be used into the varieties of another field like medical, agriculture, pharmaceuticals etc. [12-16].

Algae mediated synthesis of nanoparticle has been done with the help of various species ranging from Chlorophyceae, Diatoms, Phaeophyceae, Euglenoids, Cyanophyceae, Rhodophyceae etc. The nanoparticle of gold, ferrihydrite, palladium, silver and many more has been made as a result. In another work, the fact that production of the magnetic nanoparticle-mediated through algae could lead to enhancement of growth and lipid formation in cyanobacteria and microalgae is established [15-17].

2. TYPES OF NANOPARTICLES

Molecular base and structure base can be two criteria on which we can divide the nanoparticle. Molecular bases on further investigation can be broadly classified into organic and inorganic, where carbon nanoparticle is a major constituent of organic nanoparticles. Fullerenes are a class of organic nanoparticle consisting of the nanotubes and buckyballs. Carbon nanotube could be defined as the one atom thick sheet of graphite rolled in order to form the tube. Tubes can be further of two types single-walled and multi-walled [18, 19].

Inorganic nanoparticles are the further sum of magnetic, semiconductor nanoparticles and noble metal. Magnetic particle is formed of the element with the magnetic properties like of iron, cobalt, nickel etc. They could be manipulated with the help of an external magnetic field. Due to its variety of application in the field like those of Medicine, catalysis, magnetic particle imaging, wastewater treatment, nanofluidics and much more [20-21].

On the basis of structure, we can classify the nanoparticle into three major types, the namely tube-like structure as that of carbon nanotubes, branches like the structure of dendrimers and spherical structure of liposomes. Liposomes are vesicle or tiny bubbles being made up of the phospholipid by layer with the hydrophilic tail of one layer toward outside make it water soluble. While the hydrophobic tail of another layer is in contact with the earlier one making the vesicle being able to carry the water-soluble drug inside of liposomes. It is basically today being applied to deliver the required biomolecules or drug etc. [22].

3. BIOSYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLE WITH HELP OF ALGAE

Algal mediated biosynthesis of the nanoparticle is a three-step procedure. It began with the formation of algal extract that could be prepared either by dissolving algal extract in an organic solvent or those into the water. This could be done in the presence of boiling or heating for certain required time being. The next step is to prepare the desired molar solution of the compound whose nanoparticle has to be formed, which is further followed by incubation of ionic metallic compound followed by maintaining of the required environment or else we could provide continuous stirring. Our choice of algae and ionic metallic compound

could majorly affect our required due course of action and our judgments of going through the intra-cellular and extra-cellular fashion of synthesis [23-25].

Table 1. Characteristics of the metal nanoparticles biosynthesized by various classes of cyanobacteria.

Algae	Species	Size of NPs (nm)	Type of NPs	Shape of NPs	Reference
Cyanobacteria	<i>Anabaena</i> sp.	80	ZnO	spherical	30
	<i>Lyngbya majuscula</i>	>20	Au	spherical	31
	<i>Microcoleus</i> sp.	44-79	Ag	spherical	32
	<i>Nostoc ellipsosporum</i>	137-209	Au	nanorods	33
	<i>Phormidium (Oscillatoria) willei</i>	100-200	Ag	spherical	34
	<i>Leptolyngbya tenuis</i> (as <i>Phormidium tenue</i>)	5	CdS	spherical	35
	<i>Leptolyngbya valderiana</i> (as <i>Phormidium valderianum</i>)	15 (pH 5) 411 x 32 (pH 5) 7.92 (pH 7) 24 (pH 7) 13.78 (pH 9)	Au	spherical nanorods triangular hexagonal	36

Table 2. Characteristics of the metal nanoparticles biosynthesized by various classes of microalgae.

Algae	Species	Types of NPs and shape	Reference
Chlorophyta	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Ag (rounded and rectangular)	36
	<i>Auxenochlorella (Chlorella) pyrenoidosa</i>	Au (spherical)	28
	<i>Auxenochlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Au (spherical)	37
	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Palladium (spherical)	27
	<i>Chlorococcum infusionum</i> (as <i>Chlorococcum humicola</i>)	Ag (spherical)	38
	<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	Ag (spherical)	22
	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Bimetallic Ag Au nanoalloy (spherical/round)	24
	<i>Cosmarium impressulum</i> <i>Kirchneriella lunaris</i>	Au (spherical)	25
	<i>Scenedesmus-24</i>	CdS	39
	Ochrophyta	<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	Ag

Extracellular synthesis of nanoparticle could occur because of reducing agent potential of various algal aqueous extract. It has gained the required potential due to the presence of proteins, polysaccharides, reducing sugar, pigments etc. which has the ability to induce reduction of metal ion and further to finally precipitate in form of nanoparticles. While in case of intracellular synthesis the ability to reduce the ionic metal compound is own to the fact like algal metabolism which involves respiration and photosynthesis that may be useful in case of reduction. In a work, it has been found that NADPH and NADPH reductase enzyme

found to be present in the electron transport system of either photosynthesis or of respiratory system has the potential to carry out the reduction of the metallic ion. In another study it has been found, nitrogenous enzyme too has the potential of reducing metallic ion compound like Au ions to nanoparticles [26-28].

In a separate study performed by Dahoumane et al. it has been identified that algal can lead to the synthesis of nanoparticle in intracellular fashion along in the dose-dependent line followed by the subsequent reduction of metallic ion particle into the nanoparticle and further release of it. It consequently established the fact that microalgae are evolved as a state where it could lead to the formation of bimetallic nanoalloys in a very restricted and regulated fashion. Over the period of time, It has been established that pH, type of metal, its molar concentration, temperature, duration of reducing agent can be altered in order to find out shape and size of the nanoparticle [29].

4. BIOSYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLE WITH HELP OF MICROALGAE

The silver nanoparticle has been found to have a various beneficial aspect like antifungal, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, wound healing, and also some good catalytic properties. These properties have led to the potential promise in the field of biosensor, drug delivery, ultrasound medical imaging etc. In a work, it has been suggested to use the Ag nanoparticle to create a cotton fabric with antibacterial properties. They are found useful in the creation of biosensor to sense the glucose level too. Along with a variety of algae, and species of cyanobacteria has the potential to create nanoparticles [22-26].

Synthesis of Ag nanoparticle could be achieved through various microalgae. Sharma et al. have been successful in order to form the Ag nanoparticle with help of green algal species like *Chlorella vulgaris* with significant yield. Merin et al. have tried to form and optimize the result by use of the variety of species *Chlorella salina*, *Tetraselmis gracilis*, and various diatoms too. Hence formed AgNPs were found to be pathogenic towards *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella* sp., etc. [36-38].

Chlorella pyrenoidosa is found to use in the creation of the nanoparticle ranging in 5-10 nm size, while *Chlorella vulgaris* is reported to remain viable at the 10^{-3} concentration of AgNO_3 . It also resulted in the polydisperse silver nanoparticle both as the result of intracellular as well as the extracellular in the continuously stirred environment. The particle has size dimension in between of 8-20 nm [39-40].

5. BIOSYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLE WITH HELP OF MACROALGAE

Gold nanoparticles have always in very high demand owing to fact that it has more favorable properties compare to anyone else. The properties that provide it an upper edge over other is easy preparation method, ability to be conjugated with different biocompatible compound, the scattering of light along with its non-toxicity are leading to its wide dimension of use. Today it has found its application ranging from diagnosis, photonics, electronics, therapeutics, optics, imaging, and catalysis. It can be used to detect analytes in the sensor. Once activated it could lead to suppressing cancer or tumor [42-44].

There are various microalgae and diatoms have been used till now in order to form the gold nanoparticle of different shape and sizes according to our purpose. *C. vulgaris* once employed could give us a 90% yield when incubated with 1 ml of HAuCl_4 (10 mM) and 10 ml of algal extract with mild stirring. Sicard et al. have used *Klebsormidium flaccidum*, for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles. Change in color from green to pink used as confirmation for the formation of gold nanoparticles [44-46].

Tetraselmis suecica is found to have the reduction potential in order to synthesize gold nanoparticle. Red to yellow color change gives the confirmation. *Tetraselmis kochinensis* also reported forming gold nanoparticle with the average size of 15nm when put at 28-29°C. In another study, it has been found that *C. pyrenoidosa* with vigorous stirring can lead to AuNPs [48-49].

Table 3. Characteristics of the metal nanoparticles biosynthesized by various classes of macroalgae.

Algae	Species	Types and shape of NPs	Reference
Chlorophyta	<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	Ag	42
	<i>Codium capitatum</i>	Ag	43
	<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Au	44
	<i>Rhizoclonium fontinale</i>	Au	45
	<i>Ulva (Enteromorpha) compressa</i>	Ag	46
Phaeophyta	<i>Bifurcaria bifurcata</i>	Cu	47
	<i>Sargassum vulgare</i>	Ag	48
	<i>Sargassum muticum</i>	ZnO	49
	<i>Cystophora moniliformis</i>	Ag	50
	<i>Saccharina (Laminaria) japonica</i>	Au	51
Rhodophyta	<i>Galaxaura rugosa</i> (as <i>Galaxaura elongata</i>)	Au	52

6. CONCLUSION

In the last seven to eight years there has been a significant increase in the kind of attention nanotechnology is getting. Green nanotechnology and the second generation of nanotechnology is expanding rapidly. The review was an attempt to summarize the work done in phyconanotechnology. The literature strongly adheres to the fact that algae mediated could be the break we need to commercialize the novel traits of nanotechnology. It has promised a significant contribution in the upcoming future. Algae have the wide dimension of habitat leading to further different potential that could be employed in order to optimize our result. There was not enough work done on red algae as compare to cyanobacteria and green algae. Further at the cellular level, it is yet to be utilized. And the metal-specific algae have to be sorted out.

Author Contributions: IS has done research, collected data, and wrote the manuscript. SS has proofread the manuscript, planned the format, and guided with research and collection of data. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Daniel MC, Astruc D. Gold nanoparticles: assembly, supramolecular chemistry, quantumsize-related properties, and applications toward biology, catalysis, and nanotechnology. *Chem Rev.* 2004; 104(1): 293-346.
2. Invernizzi N. Nanotechnology between the lab and the shop floor: what are the effects on labour? *J Nanoparticle Res.* 2011; 13: 2249-2268
3. Roco MC. The long view of nanotechnology development: the National Nanotechnology Initiative at 10 years. *J Nanoparticle Res.* 2011; 13: 427-445.
4. Nair B, Pradeep T. Coalescence of nanoclusters and formation of submicron crystallites assisted by *Lactobacillus* strains. *Cryst Growth Des.* 2002; 2(4): 293-298.
5. Lin Z, Wu J, Xue R, Yang Y. Spectroscopic characterization of Au³⁺ biosorption by waste biomass of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Spectrochim Acta A Mol Biomol Spectrosc.* 2005; 61(4): 761-765.

6. Lengke MF, Ravel B, Fleet ME, Wanger G, Gordon RA, Southam G. Mechanisms of gold bioaccumulation by filamentous cyanobacteria from gold (III)-chloride complex. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2006; 40(20): 6304-6309.
7. Nowack B, Bucheli TD. Occurrence, behavior and effects of nanoparticles in the environment. *Environ Pollut*. 2007; 150: 5-22.
8. Buzea C, Blandino IIP, Robbie K. Nanomaterials and nanoparticles: sources and toxicity. *Biogeosciences*. 2007; 2: MR17-MR71.
9. Perez-de-Luque A, Cifuentes Z, Beckstead JA, Sillero JC, Avila C, Rubio J, Ryan RO. Effect of amphotericin B nanodisks on plant fungal diseases. *Pest Manag Sci*. 2012; 68: 67-74.
10. Khot LR, Sankaran S, Maja JM, Ehsani R, Schuster EW. Applications of nanomaterials in agricultural production and crop protection: a review. *Crop Prot*, 2012; 35: 64-70.
11. Doria G, Conde J, Veigas B, Giestas L, Almeida C, Assuncao M, et al. Noble metal nanoparticles for biosensing applications. *Sensors*. 2012; 12: 1657-1687.
12. Jeffryes C, Agathos SN, Rorrer G. Biogenic nanomaterials from photosynthetic microorganisms. *Curr Opin Biotechnol*. 2015; 33: 23-31.
13. Mittal AK, Chisti Y, Banerjee UC. Synthesis of metallic nanoparticles using plant extracts. *Biotechnol Adv*. 2013; 31: 346-356.
14. Kharissova OV, Dias HVR, Kharisov BI, Perez BO, Perez VMJ The greener synthesis of nanoparticles. *Trends Biotechnol*. 2013; 31: 240-248.
15. Borowitzka MA. High-value products from microalgae - their development and commercialisation. *J Appl Phycol*. 2013; 25: 743-756.
16. Fon Sing S, Isdepsky A, Borowitzka MA, Moheimani NR. Production of biofuels from microalgae. *Mitig Adapt Strateg Glob Chang*. 2013; 18: 47-72.
17. Pádrová K, Lukavský J, Nedbalová L, Čejková A, Cajthaml T, Sigler K, et al. Trace concentrations of iron nanoparticles cause overproduction of biomass and lipids during cultivation of cyanobacteria and microalgae. *J Appl Phycol*. 2015; 27: 1443-1451.
18. Gupta AK, Gupta M. Synthesis and surface engineering of iron oxide nanoparticles for biomedical applications. *Biomaterials*. 2005; 26(18): 3995-4021.
19. Gleich B, Weizenecker J. Tomographic imaging using the nonlinear response of magnetic sparticles. *Nature*. 2005; 435(7046): 1214-1217.
20. Lu AH, Schmidt W, Matoussevitch N, Bonnemann H, Spliethoff B, Tesche B, et al. Nanoengineering of a magnetically separable hydrogenation catalyst. *Angew Chem*. 2004; 116(33): 4403-4406.
21. Xie J, Lee S, Chen X. Nanoparticle-based theranostic agents. *Adv Drug Delivery Rev*. 2010; 62(11): 1064-1079.
22. Jiang J, Oberdorster G, Biswas P. Characterization of size, surface charge, and agglomeration state of nanoparticle dispersions for toxicological studies. *J Nanopart Res*. 2009; 11(1): 77-89.
23. Dahoumane SA, Djediat C, Yepremian C, Coute A, Fievet F, Coradin T, Brayner R. Recycling and adaptation of *Klebsormidium flaccidum* microalgae for the sustained production of gold nanoparticles. *Biotechnol Bioeng*. 2012; 109: 284-288.
24. Dahoumane SA, Wijesekera K, Filipe CDM, Brennan JD. Stoichiometrically controlled production of bimetallic gold-silver alloy colloids using micro-alga cultures. *J Colloid Interface Sci*. 2014; 416: 67-72.

25. Dahoumane SA, Yéprémian C, Djédiat C, Couté A, Fiévet F, Coradin T, Brayner R. A global approach of the mechanism involved in the biosynthesis of gold colloids using micro-algae. *J Nanopart Res.* 2014; 16: 2607.
26. Abdel-Raouf N, Al-Enazi NM, Ibraheem IBM. Green biosynthesis of gold nanoparticles using *Galaxaura elongata* and characterization of their antibacterial activity. *Arab J Chem.* 2017; 10(Suppl. 2): S3029-S3039.
27. Eroglu E, Chen X, Bradshaw M, Agarwal V, Zou J, Stewart SG, et al. Biogenic production of palladium nanocrystals using microalgae and their immobilization on chitosan nanofibers for catalytic applications. *RSC Adv.* 2013; 3: 1009-1012.
28. Oza G, Pandey S, Mewada A, Kalita G, Sharon M. Facile biosynthesis of gold nanoparticles exploiting optimum pH and temperature of fresh water algae *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*. *Adv Appl Sci Res.* 2012; 3: 1405-1412.
29. Parial D, Patra HK, Dasgupta AK, Pal R. Screening of different algae for green synthesis of gold nanoparticles. *Eur J Phycol.* 2012; 47: 22-29.
30. Singh G, Babele PK, Kumar A, Srivastava A, Sinha RP, Tyagi MB. Synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles using the cell extract of the cyanobacterium, *Anabaena* strain L31 and its conjugation with UV-B absorbing compound shinorine. *J Photochem Photobiol B.* 2014; 138: 55-62.
31. Chakraborty N, Banerjee A, Lahiri S, Panda A, Ghosh AN, Pal R. Biorecovery of gold using cyanobacteria and an eukaryotic alga with special reference to nanogold formation - a novel phenomenon. *J Appl Phycol.* 2009; 21: 145-152.
32. Sudha SS, Rajamanickam K, Rengaramanujam J. Microalgae mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles and their antibacterial activity against pathogenic bacteria. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 2013; 51: 393-399.
33. Ali DM, Sasikala M, Gunasekaran M, Thajuddin N. Biosynthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles using marine cyanobacterium *Oscillatoria willei* NTDM01. *Dig J Nanomater Bios.* 2011; 6: 385-390.
34. Ali MD, Gopinath V, Rameshbabu N, Thajuddin N. Synthesis and characterization of Cds nanoparticles using c-phycoerythrin from the marine cyanobacteria. *Mater Lett.* 2012; 74: 8-11.
35. Parial D, Pal R. Biosynthesis of monodisperse gold nanoparticles by green alga *Rhizoclonium* and associated biochemical changes. *J Appl Phycol.* 2015; 27: 975-984.
36. Barwal I, Ranjan P, Kateriya S, Yadav SC. Cellular proteins of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* control the biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles oxido-reductive. *J Nanobiotechnol.* 2011; 9: 1-12.
37. Elumalai S, Santhos BI, Devika R, Revathy S. Collection, isolation, identification, and biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using microalga *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*. *Nanomechanics Sci Technol Int J.* 2013; 4: 59-66.
38. Jena J, Pradhan N, Dash BP, Sukla LB, Panda PK. Biosynthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles using microalga *Chlorococcum humicola* and its antibacterial activity. *Int J Nanomater Bios.* 2013; 3: 1-8.
39. Jena J, Pradhan N, Aishvarya V, Nayak RR, Dash BP, Sukla LB, et al. Biological sequestration and retention of cadmium as CdS nanoparticles by the microalga *Scenedesmus-24*. *J Appl Phycol.* 2015; 27(6): 2251-2260.
40. Mohseniazar M, Barin M, Zarredar H, Alizadeh S, Shanehbandi D. Potential of microalgae and Lactobacilli in biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles. *BioImpacts.* 2011; 1: 149-152.
41. Karn B. The road to green nanotechnology. *J Ind Ecol.* 2008; 12: 263-266.

42. Kathiraven T, Sundaramanickam A, Shanmugam N, Balasubramanian T. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using marine algae *Caulerpa racemosa* and their antibacterial activity against some human pathogens. *Appl Nanosci.* 2015; 5: 499-504.
43. Naveena BE, Prakash S. Biological synthesis of gold nanoparticles using marine algae *Gracilaria corticata* and its application as a potent antimicrobial and antioxidant agent. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2013; 6: 179-182.
44. Sharma B, Purkayastha DD, Hazra S, Gogoi L, Bhattacharjee CR, Ghosh NN, Rout J. Biosynthesis of gold nanoparticles using a fresh water green alga, *Prasiola crispa*. *Mater Lett.* 2015; 116: 94-97.
45. Dhanalakshmi PK, Azeed R, Rekha R, Poonkodi S, Nallamuthu T. Synthesis of silver nanoparticles using green and brown seaweeds. *Phykos.* 2012; 42: 39-45.
46. Abboud Y, Saffaj T, Chagraoui A, Bouari AE, Brouzi K, Tanane O, Ihssane B. Biosynthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of copper oxide nanoparticles (CONPs) produced using brown alga extract (*Bifurcaria bifurcata*). *Appl Nanosci.* 2014; 4: 571-576.
47. Azizi S, Namvar F, Mahdavi M, Ahmad MB, Mohamad R. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using brown marine macroalga, *Sargassum muticum* aqueous extract. *Materials.* 2013; 6: 5942-5950.
48. Govindaraju K, Krishnamoorthy K, Alsagaby SA, Singaravelu G, Premanathan M. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles for selective toxicity towards cancer cells. *IET Nanobiotechnol.* 2015; 9(6): 325-330.
49. Azizi S, Ahmad MB, Namvar F, Mohamad R. Green biosynthesis and characterization of zinc oxide nanoparticles using brown marine macroalga *Sargassum muticum* aqueous extract. *Mater Lett.* 2014; 116: 275-277.
50. Prasad TNVKV, Kambala VSR, Naidu R. Phyconanotechnology: synthesis of silver nanoparticles using brown marine algae *Cystophora moniliformis* and their characterisation. *J Appl Phycol.* 2013; 25: 177-182.
51. Ghodake G, Lee DS. Biological synthesis of gold nanoparticles using the aqueous extract of the brown algae *Laminaria japonica*. *J Nanoelectron Optoelectron.* 2011; 6: 268-271.
52. Rajesh S, Raja DP, Rathi JM, Sahayaraj K. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Ulva fasciata* (Delile) ethyl acetate extract and its activity against *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *malvacearum*. *J Biopest.* 2012; 5: 119-128.